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AN EXPLORATORY STUDY INTO THE IMPACT OF DIGITAL WORKFORCE ON ORGANISATIONAL PERFORMANCE AT THE ROAD ACCIDENT FUND

Jeremiah Madzimure, Gavaza Tlangelani Mirelda Baloyi

Digital workforce is the future for all organisations. An organisation needs to move to the direction of automation to ensure that organisational performance is improved to an optimal level. A digital workforce will ensure that there is increased data quality and validation. The automation process will reduce the time it takes for employees to process their work. Beyond automation, the 'gig economy' is also reshaping work arrangements in key service sectors, making the informal-formal dualism, which is common in labour markets of developing countries. The purpose of the research was to investigate the impact of digital workforce on organizational performance at the Road Accident Fund in Gauteng province. The researchers endeavour to explore and understand how the digital workforce impact organizational performance. This research was conducted via a qualitative approach with the subject of insider's viewpoint. This study used 10 subjects as the sample size. When assessing the reasons behind the impact of digital workforce on organizational performance it was identified, that employee training should be prioritized for the digital workforce to be successful. Findings from the research highlighted that there is a lot of work to be done to ensure that employees are digitally equipped, and that the organization should invest in technologies that adapt to the digital environment. Having realized that the digital workforce does positively impact organizational performance the study submits the following recommendations: the Road Accident Fund to develop a digital workplace strategy that will clearly outline and define business objectives and technology priorities, provide employees with necessary training and communication on the benefits of the digital workforce, the Road Accident Fund should establish performance metrics to establish alignment to business and technology strategies and the Road Accident Fund in Gauteng province should establish automation capabilities

Keywords: digital workforce, organisational performance, Road Accident Fund, Gauteng province, South Africa

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1. Introduction

Digital workforce is the future for all organisations. An organisation needs to move to the direction of automation to ensure that organisational performance is improved to an optimal level. A digital workforce will ensure that there is increased data quality and validation. The automation process will reduce the time it takes for employees to process their work. Beyond automation, the 'gig economy' is also reshaping work arrangements in key service sectors, making the informal-formal dualism, which is common in labour markets of developing countries. These work arrangements range from online labour markets for task-based work, conducted remotely and managed digitally, to on-demand platform work, such as food deliveries and transportation [1].

According to [2], an acknowledgement of the implications of digital technology and of the necessity for a broader approach in overseeing and dealing with the effect of such advancements contributes to the uncertainty of what the future holds. [2] reiterates that the world's reliance on technology has pervaded society, affecting all industries of the economy. In a nation of high inequality,

such as South Africa, this effect further perpetuates disparity [3].

Claimants and stakeholders submit all correspondences to the organisation in a paper format. The documents are submitted to the mailroom and scanned for record purposes, then after the scanning process is done the documents are delivered to other departments in the organisation. When these documents reach the person who they are directed to, the person needs to first request the file from Archives department, so that the document can be filed in the physical file. The whole process is time consuming and it delays the response time to give feedback to claimants or stakeholders. The Road Accident Fund uses a paper-based environment where files and documents are stored and retrieved manually. This kind of environment poses a huge risk where documents can be lost, misfiled, or damaged before they can reach the physical file where they should be stored.

Files that are stored offsite are still requested back to the office for audit queries or new documents that need to be filed inside the physical file. The continuation of paper use is not good for the environment, it is not

helping the organisation to save the planet. The study is being conducted for the organisation to realise the impact of a digital workforce, how it can improve organizational performance and assist the company to be more efficient.

This research explores how a digital workforce can increase organisational performance at the Road Accident Fund in Gauteng province. Due to the pandemic the need for employees to work remotely has increased and organisations still need quality work for their client's.

This pandemic reinforced the importance of digital agility for instances when the unexpected happens. Agility is the ability to adapt and respond rapidly to events and changing conditions [4]. Therefore, whatever happens an organisation will be able to function, thanks to the digital enablement", says Garsen Naidu, country manager, Cisco South Africa.

The findings of this study will be to highlight the importance of a digital workforce and how it will increase organisational performance. The need for the organisation is to invest on a digital workforce and for management to buy it, so that employees can realise the how a digital workforce can benefit the organisation. The study will add value to the body of knowledge because of unpacking the impact of digital workforce on organisational performance at the Road Accident Fund in Gauteng Province.

2. Literature review

The aim of this literature review is to provide an overview on how work will continue to change in the next coming years, but even more to gain insights on the impact of digital workforce on the organisational performance. A review of secondary sources in the field of digital workforce will be undertaken. Hence, sources were chosen that are cited by most other sources, while generally solely credible papers, journals, and books were used. However, because humans are naturally biased according to their background, expertise and opinion on the subject matter [5], therefore the researcher will get a second opinion in respect to the sources that would be used in the study.

Conception of digital workforce

The digital workforce has developed many competencies during their interactions with technology that may be leveraged at work. Among the most obvious of these competencies are their proficiency and comfort in achieving desired outcomes using technology, often referred to as "digital fluency" [6].

With the increasing prevalence of technology in everyday life, even entry-level workers may join the workforce with high levels of digital fluency. This competency can be valuable to organizations in several different ways. The digital workforce will likely be comfortable with technology-based instruction [7].

It is important for organisations to compete in today's technological environment and still maintain a working environment that meets the organisation's per-

formance. According to [8] most digital technologies provide opportunities for improvements but if the organization lacks the right mind-set or have flawed processes, the technology will simply magnify the problems. [9] point out that organizations that successfully have managed transformations, have focused on changing the mind-set of the employees as well as the organizational culture and processes before they have decided what tools to use or how to use them [9]. Digitisation has changed the way things are done in the world from shopping, education, work and online doctor's appointments. It has reduced the need for human interaction. Organisations are allowing employees to working anywhere due to the digital workforce.

The benefits of digital workforce

The benefits and importance of the digital workforce cannot be overemphasized. Organisations in first world countries shifted to the digital environment a long time ago, while companies in developing countries are moving rapidly towards the digital workforce now. The Covid-19 pandemic has forced organisations to invest in a digital workforce that would allow organisations to remain productive during the hard lockdown, which happened in 2020. A digital workplace, however, is not only about technology or tools. It is fundamentally about a completely new business culture with new processes and ways of working [5, 10]. The digital workforce has a great impact on organisational performance. [10] puts forward the view that the digital workplace can be thought of as a master key, which unlocks all resources an organization has to offer an employee to do his/her work. By integrating new technologies into strategic processes, digital transformation aims to change business operations, processes, and services [11, 12]. According to [13], this digital revolution has taken by storm all aspects of our daily lives and the way we work is one of the areas where the revolution strongly affects the employees. Technologies, such as cloud computing, mobile apps, e-commerce or wireless communication, have helped democratize information and give access to knowledge at a larger scale than ever before.

It is widely acknowledged, that a digital workplace can optimize workforce productivity and much research has been conducted about its benefits, such as increased collaboration, better compliance, mobility and reduced stress and overload [14, 15]. Implementing workplace technologies like mobile, cloud, analytics and social tools into the workplace will empower employees to be more productive and communicate with ease, at anytime from anywhere [10]. A digital workplace provides advantages for employees and the organization, including employee satisfaction, improved employee experience, closer collaboration, reduced operational costs, enhanced innovation, improved customer experience, and increased revenue [16].

Table 1 summarizes the benefits, gained by employees and the organization when implementing a digital workplace [10].

Table 1

Benefits of a digital workplace	
Employees	Organization
Empowers employees with a richer IT experience	Accelerates decision-making and innovation
Provides a consistent user experience across all devices	Provides more effective ways of working, increases productivity
Raises employee engagement	Speeds up the release of new products and services
Helps employees experience greater flexibility and choice	Provides efficient information distribution channels
Helps to improve employee and customer experience	Strengthens talent attraction and retention
Enables access to expert knowledge and discovery of project-critical	Prevents information overload
Improves communications interfaces and collaboration	Reduces sales cycles
Enable agility	Exploits customer-oriented styles and technologies
Prevents time, wasted in recreating information that already exists	Increases the chances of a proper successfully meeting its outcomes by using cross-functional teams
Reduces employees absenteeism	Facilitates technical improvement including better performance, platform support, improved security, etc.
Decreases staff turnover	Enables environmental gains due to a reduction in travel (thereby improving the carbon footprint)
Enables secure access for users from anywhere at any time	
Support closer collaboration with customers, partners & co-workers.	

Source [10]

Digital transformation in the workforce

According to [17], due to the rapid development of digitalization, businesses have come under pressure to overcome fierce competition and technological change. Shifting from traditional services, a wide range of automated banking services are recently seen in the industry [18]. The [19] estimates that by 2020 over 50 % of employees will require significant reskilling and up skilling. This will be a huge task for HR and other managers, especially since 80 % of 2030 jobs do not exist yet [20]. “Transformation leadership skills are essential and require the active involvement of the different stakeholders, affected by the transformation” [21]. A digital transformation does not only remove the distance barrier between people but creates a sense of space of its own [22]. The cyberspace, in which participants are given the sense of occupying the same space, although they are physically not at the same location, enables multiple virtual interactions next to the number of interactions one already has in the ‘real-world’[23]. There are three fundamental trends that have been driving the need for a digital workplace, information overload, the need for speed, and population aging [11].

Digital empowerment

Digital empowerment refers to the ability of an individual to use technologies in order to develop and strength his or her capacity within information society [24].

Organisations should ensure that they digitally empower employees to enable them to compete in the digital workforce. This will allow employees to be able to manage and do their work and still meet organisational performance. Organisations should invest in infrastructure that will adapt to all the technological changes that are happening in the world of technology. Technology needs to be selected based on how it aligns with the organization’s strategy and what value it brings to the business [25]. Thus, a cross-functional

team, consisting of senior leaders, IT, HR and Marketing should be formed to create a digital workplace strategy that clearly articulates what business goals the strategy intends to solve and how digital solutions should be developed [10].

Organisations will not survive if they do not adopt changes in the workplaces. [26] New markets are arising, while businesses profiting from only one, now outdated, product are losing their market share. For these, it is time to rethink their strategy and use the digital transformation to reinvent and update their product. [27].The digital revolution has displaced many middle-skilled jobs, while high-skilled jobs are on the rise, requiring more problem solving and overall skills, as a result of which many researchers argue that the shift to an increase in knowledge-based organizations is on the rise [28].While digitization is more about systems of record and increasingly systems of engagement, digitalization is about systems of engagement and systems of insight, leveraging digitized data and processes [29]. New technologies work is often shifted to home office arrangements, giving employees the freedom to complete work outside their regular working 17 hours [30]. The proven points on what an organization will gain by introducing and embracing the digital workplace are presented in a report by [15]:

1. Attracting talent – 64 % of employees would prefer working out of with a lower pay.
2. Productivity – Having strong online social networks is 7 % more productive
3. Satisfaction – having digital, social tools shows a median increase of satisfaction by 20 %
4. Retention of employees – digital workplaces increase the employee engagement, which in its case increases the employee retention up to 87 %
5. Office workers prefer modern communication tools much like the communication tools, used privately (instant messaging).

6. According to (24), there are the main challenges to become a digital organization, which are as follows:

7. A Change-Resisting Culture

8. Various issues, related to ownership and control of different processes, information flow and systems, make people resistant to share their knowledge.

9. Always Keep in mind that digital may just not be feasible for all the parts of the organization.

10. Handling talent gap also acts as a challenge for an organization.

11. Highly structured, complex, and traditional processes may not work for digital.

12. It is often very difficult, challenging, and costly to make digital work platforms as creating an ecosystem of a network incur costs time, different resources, and lot of money.

Organisational performance at different levels in the organisation.

[28] defined organizational performance as a measurement for different levels of hierarchy that can be assessed for individuals, groups, and the entire organization. Organisational performance is one of the most important foundations that makes or breaks an organisation. It is vital to ensure, that employees in the organisation are made aware of what is required from them and why organisational performance is important for the success of the organisation. Performance in an organisation is normally divided in according to categories, which are individual, teams, departmental, division and the organisation.

At the individual level, task performance, contextual performance, adaptive performance, and counterproductive work behaviour are the main dimensions, identified in an exhaustive search of medical, psychological and management studies [31]. Personal performance can be viewed as a single repository that combines all personal, team or project related tasks, an overview of all the projects and activities an employee is associated with, an overview of metrics relevant to an employee, and direct access to other important information regardless of source [6].

Team performance, in turn, involves having virtual and dynamic spaces to enable seamless and effective collaboration regardless of time, location, group size or

the task at hand. The virtual spaces cater for the effective management of information, tasks, agendas, deadlines, contacts, and deliverables. Communication can be done synchronously or asynchronously through text, voice, video between one or several people [10]. For teams, level organizational performance to the completion of a task is an important measure [32]. Moreover, task proficiency is another indicator of good performance as team members who are proficient in their tasks are associated with higher performance levels.

[33] have reported several models of assessing team performance, ranging from Input-process-output, which takes a systems view of team processes, to looking at team tasks as events where performance measurement aids like the behaviourally anchored rating and Observation scale (BARS) and self-report measures are employed. These measures should assess the team adaptability, team orientation, leadership, and back up behaviours to measure team performance.

When assessing the organization's performance as a whole, a cohort of measures need to be adopted, so that all components can be monitored and evaluated comprehensively. In fact, there is a conscious call to move towards a broader definition of organizational performance, one which recognizes and addresses sustainability of work processes and outcomes [9]. Another key variable in measuring organizational performance is integrating a formal assessment of strategic planning in its measurement [19]. When organizations assess their strategic planning using internal and external assessments with a cascading system of goals, strategies, and plans, the effectiveness of meeting these goals is found to be improved. [8] have added that professionals need to establish a strong rationale for understanding what is meant by performance and the choice of measures that will be employed to measure it. There is a digital workplace framework that exists and it allows departments to blend into one another. The digital workplace framework consists of different building blocks that form a great foundation for the digital workforce [10] (Table 2).

Table 2

Framework for the digital workplace

Digital workplace Framework			
Personal performance – Dashboards – Activity streams – Self-services – Personal info.mgmt – Decentral data – etc.	Team performance – Collaboration – Conferencing – Project mgmt. – Etc.	Organisational performance – Social networking – Community – Idea management – Enterprise jams – etc.	Communication & information – News – Knowledge sharing – Content syndication – eLearning – etc.
Process performance – Process, Case and Information flows specific applications			Culture & Relations – Internet branding – Social Applications – Campaigning – etc.
Structures, Context & Services for all components of the digital Workplace – Search – Personalization – Analytics – Intelligent agents – Compliance			

Source [10]

Employee Engagement

[34] define employee engagement as “a positive attitude, held by the employee towards the organization and its value”. Organisation should bear in mind that the digital workforce will have to incorporate employees that are not comfortable with technology. Therefore it is important for organisations to ensure that they are able to deal with conflicts that might arise as a result of going digitally, other employees might resist change and refuse to use and work in the digital environment. Organisations should encourage employees to engage each other using the digital workspace. According to [34], employee engagement can be achieved through the creation of an organisational environment where positive emotions, such as involvement and pride, are encouraged, resulting in improved organisational performance, lower employee turnover and better health.

[35] suggested that it might be wise for organisations to consider online games to motivate employees by providing clear goals and real-time feedback that helps to track progress toward goals. Remote working enhances greater communication, collaboration and learning for employees in the organisation, this will be happening anytime and anyplace. [14] found that digital technologies play an important role in the lives of employees as well as human resource management (HRM), which indirectly impacts an organization. It focuses on the impact of these changes on HRM, in relation to changes to the workforce, to HRM in general and more specifically to the use of technology in delivering HRM activities.

According to [18], there are the main challenges to become a digital organization, which are as follows:

1. A Change-Resisting Culture
2. Various issues, related to ownership and control of different processes, information flow and systems make people resistant to share their knowledge.
3. Always Keep in mind that digital may just not be feasible for all the parts of the organization.
4. Handling talent gap also acts as a challenge for an organization.
5. Highly structured, complex, and traditional processes may not work for digital.
6. It is often very difficult, challenging, and costly to make digital work platforms as creating an ecosystem of a network incur costs time, different resources and lot of money.

Rapid changing in organisations can affect employees emotionally, it is important to ensure that they provide support to employees on how to handle the new working environment.

3. The aim and objectives of the study

The aim of the research was to highlight the importance of a digital workforce, how it will benefit the organisation and increase organisational performance.

To achieve the aim, the following specific objectives were set:

1. To investigate how the Road Accident Fund can digitally empower employees to increase performance and productivity.

2. To examine the influence of the organisation's commitment to the digital workforce on organisational performance at the Road Accident Fund.

3. To make recommendation to the Road Accident Fund, Gauteng, on how a digital workforce can boost employee's engagement and satisfaction.

4. Materials and methods

For the purposes of this study, exploratory research was adopted because of the high level of uncertainty in this study. The researchers needed to understand the impact of digital workforce on organisational performance.

To analyse the impact of the digital workforce on organizational performance, the study employed qualitative research methods to answer questions about experience, meaning, and perspective, as a result, the methods were suitable for the study [36]. The advantage of using qualitative research is that the data obtained is based on human experiences, which is a very important aspect in understanding the impact of the digital workforce. Additionally, qualitative research processes are real life, as a result, the processes allowed the researcher to develop an accurate understanding of the effectiveness of the digital workforce on employees.

The case study strategy was employed to investigate the impact of digital workforce on organisational performance at the Road Accident Fund in Gauteng province.

The target population was all 151 employees at the Road Accident Fund in Gauteng province. A sample size of 10 was adequate to yield insight into a phenomenon and answers of the research question. The convenience sampling method was used to collect data. This study followed the ethical considerations. The participants were given informed consent prior to data collection. No participants were forced to take part in this study against their will and as well all participants were told that they can withdraw at any given time should they wish to do so with no consequences.

5. Research results and discussion

The Demographic Information of the participants.

The demographic information of the 10 participants who were interviewed consists of the following subcategories:

1. Age
2. Gender
3. Level of Education
4. Years of service at the Road Accident Fund

Age of Respondents

The participants interviewed range from age group 30 and above. 20 % is between category 30 to 32, 20 % – 39 to 45 and 60 % – 46 and above (Table 3).

Views from the 18 to 35 age group will add different perspective.

Whilst [37] notes with concern that while youth unemployment is extremely high in South Africa, youth between the ages of 18 and 25 is however less likely to start their businesses.

Table 3

Age	Number of respondents	Percentage	Percentage
18–25	0	0	0
26–35	2	20	20
36–45	2	20	20
46–above	6	60	60
Total	10	100	100

Gender of Participants

The gender mix of the participants was Female-dominated as in 60 % males compared to 40 % females. Whilst data is leaning towards female domination in business, men have been dominating the business work for decades (Table 4).

Table 4

Gender	Male	Female	Total
Number of Respondents	4	6	10
Percentage	40 %	60 %	100 %

Level of Education

The level of education amongst the 10 participants is as follows:

- 3 diplomas
- 1 higher certificate or grade 12
- 3 postgraduate diplomas
- 3 Bachelor's degree (Table 5)

The observation is that the level of education is enough for employees at the Road Accident Fund although an improvement in the level of education will always be encouraged. Literature from [38] finds that there is a positive correlation between exposure to entrepreneurship education and attitudes towards becoming an entrepreneur. In other words, entrepreneurs with a higher level of educations have a greater probability of success as an entrepreneur.

Table 5

Qualification	Nr. of respondents	Percentage
grade 9–11	0	0
higher certificate	1	10
Diploma	3	30
BA degree	3	30
Postgraduate/Honours	3	30
Masters	0	0
Doctorate	0	0
Total	10	100

Years of Service at the Road Accident Fund

There is a lot of experience amongst the 10 respondents with 2 of the respondents in the 20–30 years' service brackets and 3 in the 15–19 years of service brackets. The years of service also emphasise that the respondents have encountered all the challenges possible within the organisation (Table 6).

Table 6

Years of service at the Road Accident Fund	nr. of respondents	Percent
1–4 years	0	0
5–14 years	5	50
15–19 years	3	30
20–30 years	2	20
Total	7	100

Topics discussed during interviews

a) In your understanding is the digital workforce an important factor in increasing organizational performance at the Road Accident Fund? Please explain.

Most, if not all, of the participants, responded to the researcher, do agree that digital workforce will increase organizational performance because employees will be able to perform their tasks anywhere and faster.

b) How can the Road Accident fund use digital workforce to empower employees to increase performance and productivity?

Participants emphasized the importance of having advanced IT infrastructures that will adapt to the changing technologies. Effective employee training programs should be implemented to ensure that employees understand what is expected from them.

c) How will the Road Accident Fund motivate employees to support a digital workforce?

Training should be continuous and the benefits of the digital workforce should be emphasized and why the organization is adopting the digital workforce.

d) What is the extent, to which the Road Accident Fund is adapting to a digital workforce?

Due to the Covid-19 pandemic, the organizations have rapidly adapted to the digital workforce by allowing employees to work from home to ensure business continuity.

e) How would you define organizational performance?

Most do agree that organizational performance is the method, used by organizations to measure targets and objectives.

f) How will the Road Accident Fund measure organizational performance at different levels?

Currently performance is measured by using a balanced scorecard that employees populate using targets that are set up at the executive level and transferred down in divisions in the organization. Employees are informed about the target and they are expected to contract on the targets that they are given.

g) What recommendations will be made to develop processes and procedures that will boost employees' engagement and satisfaction?

Most agree that they should be engagements with employees and that feedback should be given to employees.

h) What positive impact will a digital workforce bring to the Road Accident Fund?

It will save time and increase productivity for the organization, because employees will be able to do their work anywhere in the country.

i) What recommendations will be made to develop a standardized quality management system for the Road Accident Fund?

Decentralization of the process in the organization, which will ensure that there is efficiency and excellence in the way stakeholders are serviced.

Core themes analysed

Digital Employee Training

Organizations need to prioritize the reskilling and up skilling of employees, so that they can adapt to the digital workforce and this will positively impact organizational performance. The skills that they acquire during training will be used to improve performance in their current jobs. [38] discusses that in order to promote the cultural and technical changes, which are required for a successful digital transformation, a few leading firms have adopted an agile framework, designed specially to support small teams to achieve goals, related to customers, and maintain other network system within and outside the organization. [39] says that an organization must be open to new and creative employee solutions as great ideas lead to unique solutions and innovations, which is the future requirement of any company. Digital training is safe, convenient and with the pandemic that we are facing employees won't be forced to travel, this can be done online by sending learning materials to employees.

Organizations should ensure that they reduce the digital skill gap in the organization because continuously empowering your employees will increase efficiency, training provides employees in the organization the opportunity to learn and develop new technical skills that give them the confidence in doing their jobs and becoming innovative. The analysis of data, received from the respondents, highlights the importance of training employees on using digital tools. Respondent A stated that:

“Educate employees on the intersection between business and technology that need innovative digital solutions” and

Respondent B states that: *“: the employer has to take the employees for training, in order for them to be in tune of using the digital tools.”*

IT infrastructures that supports the digital workforce

The technologies that organizations use should be able to support the new way of working. It is important for the organization to invest on top of the range IT infrastructures that will adapt to the digital workforce. For the workplace to be effective and the technology to deliver added value, the workplace must be enhanced by context, structured and unstructured data, and consistent coverage of information flows [6]. The Covid-19 pandemic has placed a lot of pressure on organizations to ensure that they adapt to the changes in order to survive, without the right IT infrastructure they would mostly not survive during this period.

It is widely agreed, that a digital workplace can solve many of the information-related problems organizations are facing, helping employees and the organization to perform better [10]. This can only be achieved if organizations fully support employees by providing them with tools that properly function and are user friendly. One respondent stated that:

“Implement and maintain ICT networks that are fit for purpose and built to service customer needs in cost-effective way that ensures best value”

The participants do agree that the organization is on the right track when it comes to the digital workforce but the employer should ensure that all the employees are digitally equipped, so that this can impact on organizational performance, and that employees should be supported by the IT department, especially when they are working remotely.

Research limitations. This study was one performed in one province of the country, which might make generalisations of these results difficult.

Prospects for further research. The following future research that is related to this study can be of benefit if it is done on:

1. The impact of Automation at the Road Accident Fund
2. The impact of a paperless environment at the Road Accident Fund.

6. Conclusion

The digital workforce is the new way of business and organization that should fully support the digital workforce because it positively impacts on organizational performance because it allows employees to continue doing their work anywhere and anytime. Employees should be digitally empowered that will make them more efficient and effective. For the digital workforce to impact positively on organizational performance, the organization should invest on infrastructures that will enable all the departments to be fully digital.

Due to the qualitative research design, the researcher sourced data from 10 employees at the Road Accident Fund in Gauteng province using convenience sampling, resulting in the conclusions, not being generalizable beyond the specific population from where the sample was drawn. Covid-19 impacted the contact between the researcher and the respondents, however respondents opted to respond via email. However, the researcher surely hopes that the lessons, learnt from the study, will be pliable to the Road Accident Fund.

1. Having realized that the digital workforce does positively impact organizational performance, the study submits the following recommendations:

2. The Road Accident Fund to develop a digital workplace strategy that will clearly outline and define business objectives and technology priorities.

3. Provide employees with necessary training and communication on the benefits of the digital workforce.

4. The Road Accident Fund in Gauteng province should establish performance metrics to establish alignment to business and technology strategies.

5. The Road Accident Fund in Gauteng province should establish automation capabilities.

Conflicts of interest

The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest.

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Jeremiah Madzimure*, Centre for Academic Development/Department of Education, Vaal University of Technology, Potgieter blvd., Vanderbijlpark, South Africa, 1900

Gavaza Tlangelani Mirelda Baloyi, Mancosa College, 26 Aliwal str., Durban, South Africa, 4001

**Corresponding author: Jeremiah Madzimure, e-mail: jeremiahm@vut.ac.za*